

Monte Carlo Study of Photoneutron Effects in CANDU Reactors

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ABSTRACT

This study quantifies the deuterium photoneutron yields from both prompt (fission) gammas and delayed (decay) gammas, considering burnup and power conditions representative of a bundle in a CANDU reactor, with the most up-to-date photon and deuterium (γ,n) reaction data libraries. Comparison with experimental data adopted by industry reveals discrepancies, notably in the short- and long-lived decay photoneutron parameter and the photonuclear yields. The results of this study call into question the accuracy of historical experiments and the need for further experimental validation.

Keywords: CANDU, photoneutrons, photonuclear, heavy water

1. INTRODUCTION

Photoneutrons are particularly important in CANDU reactors that use heavy water as moderator and coolant. The deuterium nucleus has a binding energy of 2.2 MeV, enabling photodisintegration (γ,n) reactions when exposed to high-energy photons produced by fission and subsequent fission-product decay. Although the absolute number of photoneutrons is small compared to the delayed-neutron population and even smaller compared to the prompt neutron population, they have an important role in CANDU reactor kinetics. Delayed photoneutrons behave like additional groups of delayed neutrons, effectively increasing the delayed neutron fraction by several percent.

Delayed photoneutron parameters have traditionally been determined from experimental measurements quantifying the photoneutron yield per fissionable isotope. One of the earliest studies by S. Bernstein [1] examined the neutron irradiation of fissile materials and reported an absolute yield of 0.00085 photoneutrons per U-235 fission. This value was later revised to 0.00026 per U-235 fission by N.P. Baumann *et al.* [2], based on improved experimental methods. A subsequent evaluation by R.T. Jones [3] reassessed these earlier results using measurements from the ZED-2 research reactor and complementary modeling techniques. Based on this work, Baumann's value for the U-235 decay fission yield was recommended for continued use, while the yields for the additional fissioning isotopes found in CANDU fuel (U-238, Pu-239, and Pu-241) were provided by R.T. Jones. The relative group yields and half-lives for the photonuclear group parameters were established from Laughton's [4] literature review, and validated by R.T. Jones with rod-drop experiments [3]. These parameters have since been adopted as the standard for CANDU reactor transient analysis.

More recently, computational methods have been employed by E.T. Rand *et al.* [5] to re-examine the recommended photonuclear group parameters [4] for thermal fission in heavy water, highlighting potential inaccuracies in the underlying experimental data. Y.A. Setiawan *et al.* [6] further investigated the photonuclear yields per fission product in a CANDU 37-element bundle, accounting for ring-dependent power distribution. As noted by Setiawan, the available literature on photonuclear yields considering the CANDU geometry remains limited, with no literature to date examining the effects of burnup dependence or full-core modeling. The present work addresses these gaps by providing a comprehensive analysis of both prompt and delayed photoneutron production in a 37-element bundle and full-core configuration considering burnup and power conditions consistent with CANDU reactor.

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2. Methodology

A coupled Monte Carlo–deterministic computational approach was employed to evaluate prompt and delayed photoneutron production in a representative 37-element CANDU fuel bundle and a full-core model. Lattice-cell deterministic simulations were performed using the TRITON and NEWT, modules of the SCALE code system [7], to generate burnup-dependent cross-section libraries. These libraries were used to compute delayed high-energy gamma emissions with ORIGEN [7], which tracks 2,297 isotopes and includes photon libraries containing discrete line energies and intensities for 1,132 radionuclides. This spectrum was discretized into 45 energy groups extending from 2.22 MeV to 14.0 MeV, with finer resolution at lower energies.

MCNP [8] was then used to evaluate the prompt high-energy gamma intensity and corresponding photonuclear yield, either directly using the LA150U library [9] or by tallying the spatial and energy distributions of photon fluxes. For the latter process, the photon fluxes were combined with the energy-dependent deuterium (γ, n) cross sections to obtain photonuclear reaction rates using the 45-energy group structure. For the delayed photon spectrum, the photonuclear yields were derived through a series of MCNP photon transport simulations for each discrete energy group, enabling reconstruction of photonuclear yield at each timestep of activation and decay.

The CANDU 37-element bundle geometry includes 37 fuel pins grouped into four radial regions corresponding to their concentric ring arrangement. The initial fuel composition is natural uranium with an enrichment of 0.72 wt%, with a total of 19.3 kg of uranium per bundle. The coolant and moderator consist of heavy water with purities of 99.3% and 99.97%, respectively. The lattice cell has a square pitch of 28.575 cm by 28.575 cm, and the three-dimensional model extends 49.53 cm in length. The fuel density is scaled to maintain the total uranium mass per bundle, as the models exclude the end plates. The full-core model, representative of a CANDU-6 reactor, comprises 380 fuel channels with 12 bundles per channel. Two major reactivity control devices are included in the model: the fully inserted adjuster rods and the liquid zone controllers (LZCs), filled to just below half (0.45).

Y. A. Setiawan [6] demonstrated that the photonuclear yields of fission products in CANDU bundle are influenced by the ring-dependent power distribution and burnup profile. Accordingly, the lattice-cell model generating delayed gamma libraries incorporates the four ring-based structure based on the power distribution.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. CANDU-6 Bundle High-Energy Gamma Emissions

Gamma emission during the operational lifetime of a fuel bundle is influenced by the reactor power and fuel burnup. Prompt high-energy gamma rays, produced directly from fission, scale proportionally with the bundle power. This trend is also observed and confirmed for high-energy decay gammas, as shown in Figure 1, where the decay gamma data overlap when the high-energy gamma emission is normalized to reactor power.

Aside from fissions in U-235, CANDU fuel bundles experience an increasing contribution from Pu-239 fission as burnup progresses. This shift affects both the prompt high-energy gammas generated directly from fission and the decay gammas emitted by fission products. Over 99% of the high-energy prompt gamma radiation is direct fission-produced gamma, with minimal contributions from bremsstrahlung (0.1%), and no contribution from positron annihilation and fluorescence processes (which do not produce photons with energies exceeding 2.2 MeV). Over the lifetime of the fuel bundle, the prompt gamma emissions increase with burnup, producing approximately one high-energy gamma per fission, contrary to the decay gamma that decreases over the lifetime of the bundle. Overall, prompt gammas account for roughly eight times more high-energy photons than delayed gammas. However, the high-energy decay gammas exhibit a slightly higher average energy of about 2.97 MeV, compared to approximately 2.5 MeV for prompt gammas.

Figure 1: Prompt and decay high-energy gamma (>2.2 MeV) emissions for a CANDU-6 fuel bundle. The low, nominal, and high power decay gamma are not distinguishable in the figure, meaning that the decay gamma scales with power.

3.2. Fission Product Gamma-Emitting Precursors

The characteristics of delayed neutrons, including their group parameters, can be attributed to numerous distinct precursor nuclides, but it is customary to just group them into few delayed-neutron groups by decay constant. Similarly, the delayed photoneutrons created by gamma-emitting fission products are not customarily associated with distinct precursor radionuclides but rather grouped into photoneutron delayed groups as well. This avoids complications associated with the fact that there are many identified high-energy gamma-emitting fission products that contribute more evenly to the total gamma intensity. Furthermore, some of these radionuclides are formed in second and subsequent steps of fission-product decay chains. In this study, rather than attempting to identify and analyze each individual precursor radionuclide, the total high-energy gamma intensity is used to characterize the saturation behavior and decay time.

As shown in Figure 2, the high energy gamma saturation curve for a fresh fuel bundle is reached within four hours of operation with most saturation occurring immediately, regardless of the power. This behavior is examined further in Figure 3, where the 17 most significant high-energy gamma-producing isotopes representing over 50% of the total high-energy photons are examined. Although certain isotopes, such as La-142, require longer periods of saturation suggesting contribution from subsequent fission decay chains, the majority of isotopes reach saturation within the first few seconds from fission. Therefore, the time for the fission decay chains to reach saturation was not considered in the photonuclear decay group parameters.

Figure 4 illustrates the reduction of high-energy gamma emissions over decay periods ranging from seconds to hours for the nominal case at different burnup levels. Most high-energy gamma-emitting isotopes decay within the first minute, followed by a continued exponential decrease. Due to the similarities between burnup and gamma emission decay for the first couple of hours, only the mid-burnup value of 4000 MWd/Mg is adopted for the fission product gamma decay profile. This finding also implies that the delayed photonuclear group parameters reported per fissile isotope in the literature may be unnecessary, as the decay profiles of high-energy saturated radionuclides remain largely unaffected throughout burnup of a CANDU bundle.

Figure 2: High energy decay gamma intensity of a fresh fuel bundle

Figure 3: Significant high-energy gamma-producing isotopes for a fresh fuel bundle at nominal power

Figure 4: High-energy gamma decay profiles for different burnup conditions under nominal reactor power. As shown in (a), the profiles are indistinguishable at short decay times, while in (b), noticeable deviations occur at longer decay times for the 100 and 500 MWd/Mg cases.

3.3. Photoneutron Yields

Only two photonuclear libraries provide (γ, n) cross sections for deuterium: ENDF/B-VIII.1 [10], distributed by Los Alamos National Laboratory (LANL) and largely based on the IAEA-coordinated evaluation completed in 2000 [11], and JENDL-5 [12], distributed with the JENDL/PD-2016.1 dataset [13]. The JENDL-5 library exhibits a more pronounced peak in the (γ, n) cross section, which is expected to result in a higher photonuclear yield.

The photoneutron yields were simulated directly in MCNP using ENDF/B-VIII.1, which provides continuous-energy photonuclear cross-sections. For the delayed gamma contribution, the photon energy was discretized into 45 groups ranging from 2.22 MeV to 14 MeV, using 0.1 MeV intervals up to 3 MeV, 0.2 MeV intervals up to 10 MeV, and additional interval boundaries at 12 and 14 MeV. Separate MCNP photon transport calculations were then performed for each energy bin to determine the corresponding photonuclear yield. The photonuclear yields for the JENDL-5 library were computed using the photon fluxes tallied in the moderator and coolant with the interpolated (γ, n) cross-sections discretized into the same 45-group energy structure. As illustrated in Figure 5, this approximation demonstrates good agreement with the continuous-energy cross-section representation from ENDF/B-VIII.1.

Table 1 compares the recommended delayed photonuclear yields per fissile isotope from R. T. Jones [3] with the values computed using the ENDF/B-VIII.1 and JENDL-5 nuclear data libraries. The yield per isotope was evaluated individually for each fissile species through four separate activation analyses, using only the fission yield of the specified isotope. To provide a more meaningful basis for comparison, the results were presented for the operational time of a CANDU 37-element (37R) fuel bundle, as illustrated in Figure 6, computed using the fission reaction rates and neutron yields per burnup interval.

The delayed photonuclear yield reported by R. T. Jones [3] is higher than the corresponding values computed using the ENDF/B-VIII.1 and JENDL-5 libraries over the operational lifetime of the fuel bundle. Specifically, the delayed photoneutron yield decreases from 0.00031 to 0.00024 according to R.T.

Jones [3], from 0.00028 to 0.00020 using ENDF/B-VIII.1, and from 0.00032 to 0.00022 using JENDL-5. The corresponding equilibrium burnup values (based on 4,000 MWd/Mg) are 2.66×10^{-4} , 2.3×10^{-4} and 2.5×10^{-4} , respectively.

Table 1: Delayed photonuclear yield per fissile isotopes¹

	Yield Parameter	U-235	U-238	Pu-239	Pu-241
R. T. Jones [3]	Delayed Yield, $v_d^{(y,n)}$ (per fission)	0.000317 (±11%)	0.000397 (±12%)	0.000199 (±12%)	0.000279 (±14%)
	Delayed Fraction, $\beta_0^{(y,n)}$ (per fission neutron)	1.30×10^{-4}	1.40×10^{-4}	6.9×10^{-5}	9.5×10^{-5}
ENDF/B-VIII.1	Delayed Yield, $v_d^{(y,n)}$ (per fission)	0.000283	0.000345	0.000157	0.000209
	Delayed Fraction, $\beta_0^{(y,n)}$ (per fission neutron)	1.17×10^{-4}	1.24×10^{-4}	5.49×10^{-5}	7.09×10^{-5}
JENDL-5	Delayed Yield, $v_d^{(y,n)}$ (per fission)	0.000319	0.000388	0.000177	0.000235
	Delayed Fraction, $\beta_0^{(y,n)}$ (per fission neutron)	1.31×10^{-4}	1.40×10^{-4}	6.18×10^{-5}	7.96×10^{-5}

Figure 5: Photonuclear yield of prompt and decay gamma for a nominal power CANDU 37R fuel bundle

Figure 6: Delayed photonuclear yield comparing computational results from ENDF and JENDL-5 to the results by R.T. Jones [3]

3.4. Delayed Photoneutron Parameters

As noted earlier, it is not straightforward to derive the photonuclear delayed group parameters from decay characteristics of individual precursor nuclides. More than sixty radionuclides contribute to the total high-energy gamma intensity, with the top seventeen most significant contributing radionuclides only contributing to half of the total high-energy emissions. Rather than categorizing the precursor nuclides into distinct groups, the total gamma intensity from all contributing radionuclides was therefore used to define the delayed photoneutron group parameters.

In the literature, the delayed photonuclear groups parameters are often reported per fissile isotope. However, as shown in Figure 4, the decay profile of high-energy gamma emissions remains consistent

¹ The stochastic uncertainty from the Monte Carlo method is negligible in the presented results (<0.1%).

throughout the burnup of a CANDU bundle. Therefore, the photoneutron group parameters in this work are defined on a bundle basis rather than per fissile isotope.

The relative group yields and corresponding half-lives currently adopted by the CANDU industry are presented in Table 2 [3], [4]. A normalized comparison with the photonuclear yields predicted in this study (Figure 7) using ENDF/B-VIII.1 nuclear library indicates that the recommended delayed photonuclear parameters underpredicts both the short and long lived group fractions. This behavior is further illustrated in Table 2, where the predicted photonuclear decay curve is fitted using the trust-region method [14] for non-linear least-squares fitting with the same half-life group structure. This result is consistent with the findings from E.T. Rand [5] that analyzed the group parameters per fissile isotope.

Table 2: Delayed Photonuclear Parameters

Group #	Half Life	Laughton [4]	Result Fitted Group Yields
1	307.6 h	0.0011	0.0056
2	53 h	0.0023	0
3	4.4 h	0.0073	0.0057
4	5924 s	0.0527	0.0687
5	1620 s	0.0466	0.0717
6	462.1 s	0.0757	0.0343
7	144.1 s	0.1576	0.1789
8	55.7 s	0.0448	0.1186
9	22.7 s	0.2239	0.2091
10	6.22 s	0.194	0.0454
11	2.3 s	0.194	0.2621

(a)

(b)

Figure 7: Decay profile of the photonuclear yields normalized to the initial source from ENDF/B-VIII.1 predicted yield and Laughton [4]. Figure (a) displays the decay curve in the first hour and (b) displays for a longer duration.

3.5. Effective Delayed Photoneutron Fraction

The effective delayed photoneutron fraction ($\beta_{\text{eff}}^{(y,n)}$), as shown in Equation 1, was evaluated by directly comparing the multiplication factors obtained from two separate continuous energy coupled neutron photon MC simulations, one with and without the photoneutron production from the deuterium nucleus. It was shown by R.K. Meulekamp [15] that β_{eff} can be expressed in terms of reactivity by making use of the fact that χ and ν are comprised of the prompt components (χ_p, ν_p) and delayed components (χ_d, ν_d).

$$\beta_{\text{eff}}^{y,n} = \frac{P_{\text{d,eff}}^{y,n}}{P_{\text{eff}}} = \frac{\int (\phi')(\chi_d)(\nu_d)(\Sigma_f)(\phi)}{\int (\phi')(\chi)(\nu)(\Sigma_f)(\phi)} = \frac{\langle \chi_d \nu_d \rangle}{\langle \chi \nu \rangle} = 1 - \frac{\langle \chi \nu_p - (\chi_d - \chi) \nu_d \rangle}{\langle \chi \nu \rangle} \quad (1)$$

Where,

P : production rate

ν : average neutron multiplicity per fission (ν_d) for the delayed neutron (ν_p) for prompt neutron

Σ_f : is the macroscopic fission cross section,

ϕ : neutron flux,

ϕ' : adjoint flux,

χ : energy spectrum of generated neutrons (χ_d) for the delayed neutron (χ_p) for prompt neutron

With the approximation that $\nu_p \gg \nu_d$ by four orders of magnitude for the delayed photoneutrons, the factor $(\chi_d - \chi)\nu_d$ is removed. Using the same assumption, the energy spectrum of the generated photoneutrons would not have a significant impact on the total energy spectrum ($\chi \cong \chi_p$), therefore the β_{eff} can be written in terms of the multiplication factor as:

$$\beta_{\text{eff}} = 1 - \frac{\chi_p \nu_p}{\langle \chi \nu \rangle} \cong 1 - \frac{k_p}{k} \quad (2)$$

The underlying assumption for the direct k-eigenvalue comparison approach is that the stable components of the effective delayed production rate (P_{eff}), such as the flux (ϕ) and adjoint flux (ϕ'), remain consistent between the two simulations (i.e. $\phi_p \cong \phi$). This argument was originally developed for delayed neutrons. However, this assumption is more justified for photoneutrons, given that the total photoneutron yield is much smaller than even the delayed neutron contribution. This implies a negligible perturbation to the overall flux distribution.

Only photoneutrons originating from prompt gamma emissions can be directly modeled within a single MCNP simulation. Therefore, an equivalence assumption was made that the reactivity contribution from prompt gamma-induced photoneutrons $P_{\text{prompt}}^{(\gamma, n)}$ is proportional to that of the delayed photonuclear production rate $P_d^{(\gamma, n)}$. This approximation is justified by the earlier argument that the perturbation to the neutron flux from delayed photonuclear effects, on the order of 10^{-4} neutrons per fission, is negligible.

Figure 8 presents the estimated prompt and delayed photoneutron fraction over the operational lifetime of a CANDU 37R fuel bundle. The point-to-point variations in reactivity throughout the bundle's lifetime can be attributed primarily to the stochastic nature of the Monte Carlo (MC) simulation. Overall, the reactivity contributions from both prompt and delayed photoneutrons remain relatively stable, with average values of approximately 0.5 mk and 0.08 mk, respectively.

Figure 8: Prompt and delay effective photonuclear factor for a 37R CANDU fuel bundle

3.6. Full Core Simulation

Up to this point, the three-dimensional model of the CANDU bundle model was used with reflective boundary conditions. Consequently, these calculations did not account for neutron and high-energy photon leakage or consider the heavy-water reflector region surrounding the reactor core. To address this, a full-core model of the CANDU-6 containing fuel irradiated to approximately 4,000 MWd/Mg, considered an equilibrium core, was evaluated.

The prompt gamma yield increased to 1.15 high-energy photon/fission due to the structural material of the reactor, such as adjuster rods, that can cause (n, γ) reactions. Both the prompt and delayed photoneutron yields from deuterium (γ, n) reactions increased to 1.82×10^{-3} and 2.37×10^{-4} photoneutron yield from the ENDF/B-VIII.1 library, respectively. Similarly, reactivity contributions from both prompt and delayed photoneutrons increased from 0.63 mk and 0.0082 mk, respectively. These results confirm that the delayed photonuclear estimates obtained from the lattice model using reflective boundary conditions are reasonably accurate.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study aims to enhance the understanding of photoneutron production in heavy-water reactors through advanced computational modeling of CANDU fuel bundles and full-core configurations, incorporating the most up-to-date prompt and decay high-energy photon and deuterium (γ, n) reaction data libraries.

Discrepancies were identified between the simulated results and the industry-adopted data [3] derived from experimental measurements [2], most notably in the underprediction of both short- and long-lived group yields in the delayed photoneutron parameters. This trend is consistent throughout the bundle's lifetime, as the decay profile of high-energy gamma emissions remains relatively constant throughout burnup. Therefore, the delayed photonuclear group parameters are more appropriately defined on a bundle basis rather than per fissile isotope, as is commonly reported in the literature. This conclusion is further supported by the findings of E.T. Rand *et al.* [5], who reported the same trends for the group parameters per fissile isotope.

The photonuclear yields currently adopted for fissile plutonium isotopes appear to be overestimated relative to those derived from the available nuclear data libraries (ENDF/B-VIII.1 and JENDL-5). This discrepancy becomes particularly evident at higher burnup, where divergence in the photonuclear yield is observed. Between the two libraries, JENDL-5 predicts yields approximately 12–13% higher than those from ENDF/B-VIII.1.

This study calls into question the accuracy of the historical experimental values currently used for delayed photonuclear yields and photonuclear group parameters. The results suggest that reactor transient analyses of heavy-water systems may not predict the photonuclear contribution accurately, especially for longer decay transient simulations. Further experimental benchmarking of delayed high-energy gamma emissions and deuterium (γ, n) cross-section data is recommended to reduce the associated uncertainties and improve the reliability of the presented results.

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